

A study on resampling methods for handling imbalanced dataset

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Abstract- Occurrence of imbalanced classes in a dataset is one of the major issues in machine learning, as such datasets often yield biased models in favor of the majority classes instead of the minority ones. This paper discusses several techniques developed by previous researchers that help manage imbalanced datasets. This paper offers a study of resampling strategies aimed at balancing the distribution of classes using techniques such as oversampling, undersampling, and hybrid approaches. The main goal is to help researchers and practitioners choose appropriate strategies based on dataset characteristics and model requirements. By highlighting trends and real world applications, this survey serves as a guide for effectively tackling data imbalance problem.

Keywords – Imbalanced Data, Resampling, Under-sampling, Oversampling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent trends show that data has become valuable as gold. Data is a core magnet in industries like sales, marketing, advertisement, research avenues, census reports, even in the field of national security, environment monitoring, urban planning as it plays a vital role. Data hold monetary value in today's globalized world. It holds immense value as modern industries like data engineering are dependent on data. But data needs to be handled before utilizing it. Here comes a problem, because real world data is generally imbalanced in nature, where one class dominates the other class by large margin. If this problem of imbalanced data is not resolved then the machine learning model will not learn from the data, and it seriously hampers the performance. Due to this problem our data loses its core value. And if data loses its value, it may create a shut down like situation.

Fig. 1: Decision Boundary in imbalanced dataset [1]

II. BACKGROUND

Real world data is generally imbalanced in nature which is present in large volumes [2]. Various applications like detection of fraud in the banking system like credit card, where the datapoints of one class are present in large numbers and the datapoints of other class are present in small numbers [3]. The problem of imbalance class is a serious challenge, which needs to be addressed. Due to this class imbalance problem, more importance is given to the class which is in majority and less importance is given to the class which is underrepresented, which negatively impact the performance of machine learning models. As witnessed in figure 1, the decision boundary is shifted towards the class which is overrepresented, almost neglecting the samples of class which underrepresented [1].

This paper discusses various available data resampling techniques, which will help solve this problem of the imbalanced class. To resolve this challenge various techniques have been developed by the previous researchers. The techniques are broadly classified into three categories: data, algorithm and ensemble techniques as mentioned in the figure 2.

Fig. 2: Techniques To Handle Imbalanced Dataset

III. DATASETS

In machine learning, datasets are crucial because all the models performance depends on them. A critical problem arises when the data is skewed, generally characterised by the imbalanced class problem. In this problem, the datapoints of a particular class are under represented and another class is over represented. The data collected from the practical scenarios of real world is conventionally skewed and consist of class imbalance problem. Some publicly available imbalanced datasets are PLCO which stands for "Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, Ovarian", NLST (National Lung Screening Trial), BAF (Bank Account Fraud) Dataset Suite. The trial of NLST and PLCO was conducted by National Cancer Institute (NCI), USA which consists of medical data of patients available on the CDAS (Cancer Data Access System). The PLCO data contains data of 154,897 participants differently aged between 55-74 years. While the NLST data contains the data of 53,452 candidates out of which 2,058 candidates or 3.85 % have confirmed lung cancer [4]. The BAF dataset contains 1 million transactions out of which 8349 are transactions with which fraud happened.

IV. DATA LEVEL TECHNIQUES FOR ADDRESSING DATA IMBALANCE PROBLEM

To address the problem of imbalanced class at the data level several techniques have been developed to handle it effectively which are as follows:

Undersampling

Undersampling balances the dataset by reducing the number of instances in the majority class to match those in the minority class. Hence it removes the amount of information a machine learning model has to learn [5]. Although there is a risk of information loss in undersampling. The various number of undersampling methods include the following:

1. **Random Undersampling:** One of the primitive method of undersampling is random undersampling. It deliberately discards a portion of the majority class samples to achieve a more balanced dataset for training.
2. **Near miss:** The data points with minimum average distance to the nearest samples from the negative class are selected [6]. There can be different versions of Near Miss method.
3. **One sided selection:** This method eliminates only negative samples that are noisy or the samples which are redundant in the data [7].
4. **k-Nearest Neighbors:** The value of k is checked from k=1 to the given value, while removing the incorrectly classified classes in the neighbourhood [4]. It can be

classified as a non-parametric machine learning algorithm [8].

5. **Tomek Links:** Tomek Links work by identifying and removing majority class instances that are the nearest neighbors to minority class samples, helping to reduce class overlap and improve class distinction [9].
6. **Cluster Centroids:** Undersampling can be performed by substituting the majority class data points with the centroid of their respective clusters [4] [10].

The figure 3 and figure 4 gives the graphical representation of the undersampling and oversampling respectively.

Fig. 3: Graphical Representation Of Undersampling

Oversampling

Oversampling is a method employed to balance class distribution by augmenting the number of instances in the minority class, either through duplication [11] of existing samples or by generating new samples based on them [12]. The different types of oversampling methods are as follows:

- **Random Oversampling:** It is the simplest and basic method of oversampling. In random oversampling existing instances of the minority class are duplicated to increase the size of the minority class. [12]. The duplication of the samples takes place with replacement in this method [13].
- **SMOTE:** It is known as "Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique" [4]. SMOTE generates synthetic samples for the minority class by interpolating between existing instances using their k-nearest neighbors [14].
- **ADASYN:** The full form of ADASYN is Adaptive Synthetic Sampling Technique [4]. It is an advanced version of SMOTE. ADASYN tries to overcome the problem of linear interpolation of SMOTE.
- **Borderline-SMOTE:** It generates new minority class samples in neighbourhood near to the decision boundary between the classes [15].
- **SMOTE-ENN:** It is the combination of SMOTE Technique with Edited Nearest Neighbors (ENN) to address class imbalance by eliminating noisy or misclassified data points [15].
- **SMOTE-Tomek Links:** It integrates the advantages of both Tomek Links and SMOTE by applying oversampling

through SMOTE and subsequently performing undersampling using Tomek Links [4].

Fig. 4: Graphical Representation Of Oversampling

Synthetic Data Generation

With the introduction of new techniques like Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), the problem of imbalanced dataset can be further rectified. GANs are made up of two major components generator and discriminator [15]. Synthetic data points are created by the GANs without any human interference [16]. Computational complexity remains the major concern associated with GANs.

V. ALGORITHM LEVEL TECHNIQUES FOR ADDRESSING DATA IMBALANCE PROBLEM

Methods at the algorithm level include adjusting current machine learning algorithms to enhance their sensitivity to the minority class. These are also termed as the internal approach [21] because the principal concept is to address the issue of data imbalance by altering existing algorithms. These techniques involve cost-sensitive learning and class weighting methods.

Cost sensitive learning for addressing data imbalance problem

It involves various algorithms that are sensitive towards the cost involved. Several algorithms have been developed with a focus on cost sensitivity [23]. In the cost-sensitive method, changes are made in the learning process of the algorithm. These changes can be attained by the class weighting method. It is not used widely because it becomes difficult to determine the cost matrix on different datasets. The challenge here is that no universal cost strategy can be defined which suits all the datasets.

Class Weighting

This approach belongs to cost-sensitive learning, where higher importance is given to the minority class by assigning it greater weight, while the majority class is given less weight. Therefore, shifting the decision boundary towards the minority class. Different costs are associated with different tasks at hand based on their importance [24]. Researchers found that cost sensitive learning gives better results than the sampling techniques [25]. This technique is sensitive towards class weights, as small changes in weights can impact the model performance. In this technique the initial data distribution is not changed, so the decision boundary still remains biased towards the majority class.

VI. ENSEMBLE TECHNIQUES FOR ADDRESSING DATA IMBALANCE PROBLEM

Ensemble techniques integrate characteristics from both the data and algorithm techniques as well. Here, the combination of different classifiers can be used on the training data to get a judgment. A key benefit of ensemble techniques is their ability to reduce errors by leveraging multiple classifiers, where the mistakes made by one can be compensated for by others [26]. Ensemble techniques like bagging and boosting are effective to tackle the problem.

Bagging Techniques

Bagging is a technique in which multiple modules of the original dataset are created [27]. Each module of the dataset is used to train an individual learner such as decision tree. The final performance is calculated by averaging the individual performance of all the learners involved [1]. By maintaining the balance between the learners, the effectiveness of the model can be enhanced [28]. The shortcoming of bagging is that the final prediction is based on majority vote, which sometimes tends to favour the majority class.

Boosting Techniques

Boosting algorithms aim to enhance the performance of weak learners by emphasizing the training instances that were previously misclassified. The weight of the falsely classified classifiers is increased in boosting and eventually it is utilized by the new learners to predict [29]. By changing the general boosting scheme i.e. the algorithm, the different boosting approaches are classified such as AdaBoost.MH, AdaC1, AdaC2, AdaC3, AdaCost, CatBoost, GradientBoost, LightGBM, LogitBoost, MEBoost, RUSBoost, SAMME, SMOTEBoost, XGBoost [30]. The problem with boosting

Table 1: Survey on Handling Imbalanced Datasets

Name of Paper	Authors	Technology Used	Year	Cited By	Published By	Contribution
"Survey on Imbalanced Learning: Latest Research, Applications, and Future Directions" [1]	Wuxing Chen, Zhiwen Yu, Kaixiang Yang, C. L. Philip Chen, Yifan Shi [1]	Ensemble learning, imbalance regression, long-tail learning [1]	2024	124	Artificial Intelligence Review	A survey of recent methods in imbalanced learning, including regression and long-tail distributions [1].
"Handling Imbalanced Medical Datasets: Review of a Decade of Research" [17]	Mabrouka Salmi, Diego Oliva, Dalia Atif, Sebastian Ventura, Ajith Abraham [17]	Preprocessing, algorithm-level techniques, hybrid methods [17]	2024	25	Artificial Intelligence Review	Focused review on techniques tailored to medical datasets; examined trends over a 10-year span [17].
"Turning the Tables: Biased, Imbalanced, Dynamic Tabular Datasets for ML Evaluation" [18]	Sergio Jesus, Duarte Alves, Jose Pom-bal, Andre F. Cruz, Rita P. Ribeiro, Pedro Saleiro, Pedro Bizarro, Joao Gama [18]	Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) for dataset generation [18]	2022	54	Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)	Proposed a dynamic dataset generator for benchmarking ML models under class imbalance and distribution shift [18].
"A Comparative Performance Analysis of Data Resampling Methods on Imbalance Medical Data" [4]	M. Khushi, TM. Alam, K. Shaukat, S. Luo, IA. Hameed, S. Uddin, MC. Reyes, X. Yang [4]	Resampling methods (RUS, SMOTE, SMO-TEENN), Logistic Regression, Random Forest, LinearSVC [4]	2021	311	IEEE Access	Compared performance of multiple resampling strategies on medical datasets using classic ML models [4].
"Radius-SMOTE: A New Oversampling Technique of Minority Samples Based on Radius Distance" [19]	GA Pradipta, R Wardoyo, A Musdholifah, INH Sanjaya [19]	Radius-SMOTE (oversampling based on radius distance) [19]	2021	65	IEEE Access	Introduced Radius-SMOTE, an adaptive oversampling technique based on spatial distribution of data points [19].
"Survey of Imbalanced Data Methodologies" [20]	Lian Yu, Nengfeng Zhou [20]	Over-sampling, under-sampling, applied to UCI/Keel datasets [20]	2021	30	arXiv	Surveyed classical sampling methods with performance insights using benchmark datasets [20].
"A Review on Handling Imbalanced Data" [21]	VS Spelmen, R Porkodi [21]	Oversampling (SMOTE, ADASYN), undersampling, hybrid methods [21]	2018	230	IEEE	Reviewed major sampling techniques and their combinations with classifiers [21].
"Survey on Deep Learning with Class Imbalance" [5]	JM Johnson, T M Khoshgoftaar [5]	Deep learning techniques (CNN, cost-sensitive learning) [5]	2019	3036	Journal of Big Data	Surveyed deep learning methods for handling class imbalance, including CNNs and loss function modifications [5].
"Handling Imbalanced Datasets: A Review" [22]	S Kotsiantis, D Kanellopoulos, P Pintelas [22]	Oversampling, undersampling, hybrid methods [22]	2006	1553	GESTS International Transactions on Computer Science and Engineering	Provided foundational understanding of imbalance issues and reviewed resampling methods [22].

technique is that it assigns more weight to the data points which are hard to classify, which may include noise.

Hybrid Approaches

Hybrid methods combine both bagging and boosting with resampling techniques to further enhance the performance of the model [31]. It include techniques like easy ensemble, balanced cascade and others [26]. The figure 5 gives details about different types of ensemble methods.

Fig. 5: Different types of Ensemble Methods [26]

VII. EVALUATION TECHNIQUES

The various evaluation techniques to handle imbalanced datasets are as follows:

- **Precision:** Mathematically it is determined as all the True Positive (TP) cases divided by the total of True Positive (TP) and False Positive (FP) cases [32].
- **Recall:** Mathematically it is determined as the ratio of total TP cases to the total of TP and FN (False Negative) cases [32].
- **F-Measure:** Mathematically, it equals two times the product of recall and precision divided by the total of recall and precision [33].
- **AUC:** Area under curve assesses how well the model can differentiate between classes of False Positive Rate (FPR) and True Positive Rate (TPR).

VIII. DEEP LEARNING AND IMBALANCED DATA

Introduction of deep learning added new avenues for studies in the domain of data imbalance. CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) and its applications to deal with bankruptcy prediction and RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) to study intrusion detection techniques for imbalanced network are popular [33]. Researchers found that combining textual data with standard numerical data significantly boosts the performance of deep learning models in handling imbalanced datasets [34]. Computational complexity remains a concern with the deep learning techniques. However, with the advent of GANs and LLMs (Large Language Model) the research area is yet to be explored.

IX. REAL-WORLD APPLICATIONS

Imbalanced datasets are common in various fields, and addressing this issue is crucial for the machine learning model to perform well. By solving the imbalanced data problem, the various domains and their applications can be employed, which can be studied in the table 2.

X. CONCLUSION

This paper, surveyed various techniques of resampling for handling the problem associated with the imbalanced data in machine learning. This paper discusses some publicly available datasets that challenge us to tackle the imbalanced data problem. The techniques have been discussed in detail including data, algorithm and ensemble techniques along with their shortcomings. The paper also highlighted appropriate evaluation metrics for handling an imbalanced dataset. Real world applications focuses on various fields where addressing dynamic class imbalance problem, can help us create a better world to live in.

Table 2: Domains with their respective applications

Domain	Applications
Astronomy	Exoplanet discovery, rare celestial event detection
Autonomous Systems	Pedestrian or obstacle detection, accident prediction
Criminal Justice	Crime hotspot prediction, recidivism prediction
Cybersecurity	Intrusion detection, malware / phishing detection
Environmental Science	Earthquake / tornado / wildfire prediction
Finance	Loan default prediction, fraud detection
Healthcare	Rare disease detection, cancer diagnosis
Manufacturing	Equipment failure prediction, defect detection
Natural Language Processing	Hate speech detection, minority sentiment analysis
Retail	Customer churn prediction, rare purchase behavior

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